

Comparison of Hemodynamic Parameters in Severe Pre Eclamptic and Normotensive Parturients after Spinal Anesthesia during Caesarean Section

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Abstract

Introduction: Caesarean sections are now frequently performed under spinal anaesthesia to reduce the risk of airway difficulties and the medication transfer to the neonate associated with general anesthesia. Maternal hypotension following spinal anesthesia is a common side effect, even with adequate fluid loading.

Aims: In severe pre-eclamptic and normotensive parturients undergoing caesarean sections, to compare the degree of hypotension and the amount of phenylephrine required intraoperatively to treat it in order to assess the safety and effectiveness of spinal anesthesia.

Materials and Methods: The study is Observational prospective study. This study was carried out among patients scheduled for Caesarean section. Period Of Study: One and half year (March 2020 – August 2021). This study was conducted after obtaining permission from the institute's Ethical committee, scientific committee as well as approval of the West Bengal University of Health Sciences. This was conducted at obstetric operation theatre of Nil Ratan Sircar Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata, West Bengal.

Result: The percentage change of mean SBP, DBP, and MAP from baseline did not differ statistically significant between the two groups. Group A (normotensive parturients) consumed more phenylephrine than patient of group B (severe pre eclamptic parturients) and the difference was statistically significant (100.00+14.76 vs. 28.57, p= 0.006).

The incidence of hypotension was statistically significant, higher in group A (75% vs.57.1%) than in group B.

Conclusion: We compared the changes in hemodynamic parameters between severe pre-eclampsia parturients and normotensive parturients in a prospective comparative study. Although it was not statistically significant, normotensive parturients in our research had more percentage of falls of MAP than parturients with severe pre-eclampsia. Additionally, we discovered that normotensive parturients required more phenylephrine than did parturients with severe pre-eclampsia.

Keywords: Hemodynamic parameters, severe pre-eclampsia, Normotensive, Spinal anesthesia and Blood pressure.

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Introduction

Caesarean sections are now frequently done under spinal anesthesia to reduce the risk of airway difficulties and the medication transfer to the neonate associated with general anesthesia.

Maternal hypotension following spinal anesthesia is a common side effect, even with adequate fluid loading. Hypotension can result in reduced uterine blood flow, symptoms of nausea and vomiting in the

mother, and fetal hypoxia and acidosis. To avoid these detrimental consequences on parturients and newborns, it is essential to treat hypotension as soon as possible with intravenous fluids and a vasopressor. Phenylephrine is the first line therapy for hypotension after a cesarean section because it results in less fetal acidity than ephedrine.

Many studies have been conducted to find out how hemodynamics in patients with severe pre-eclampsia are affected by regional anesthesia. Examining the intraoperative phenylephrine demand, adverse fetal outcome, and intraoperative parameters of severely pre-eclamptic and normotensive parturients having spinal anesthesia is the aim of the current study.

Globally, preeclampsia/eclampsia ranks third in terms of maternal morbidity and mortality. [1]. This is especially the most prevalent cause of fetomaternal complications in developing countries, preeclampsia alone accounts for 40 to 60% of maternal deaths; in Ethiopia, hypertensive disorder during pregnancy account for 19% of maternal deaths.

Delivery is the gold standard for controlling preeclampsia and a caesarean section (CS) is often advised. [2]. An Ethiopian research found that 6.1% of CS indications were preeclampsia. A paradigm shift in the practice of obstetric anesthesia is the use of spinal anesthesia during caesarean sections rather than general anesthesia. Hypotension after spinal anesthesia has been connected to morbidity and mortality in parturients undergoing cesarean birth.

A study has shown that the combination of fluid loading and vasopressor prophylaxis reduced the incidence of spinal anesthesia-induced hypotension in healthy parturients. However, the preeclamptic patients risk of hypertension and pulmonary edema may increase as a result of these precautionary measures. [3]. the reported incidence of maternal hypotension caused by spinal anesthesia ranges between 7 and 89.2% due to conflicting definitions. As such, anesthetists face challenges when it comes to administering anesthesia to preeclamptic parturients having cesarean sections [4]. To reduce maternal deaths from risks related to pregnancy and childbirth requires safe anesthesia delivery.

Hemodynamic stability during obstetric anesthesia is a major issue for anesthetists, especially for preeclamptic parturients who are scheduled for cesarean sections [5]. However, the most frequent adverse effect caused by spinal anesthesia is maternal hypotension.

Anesthetists refused to perform spinal anesthesia for preeclamptic parturients due to the shared risk of profound hypotension and its management crisis (exaggerated response to vasopressor treatment and pulmonary edema following fluid challenges), as hypoproteinemia and pre-eclampsia are linked conditions.

Furthermore, the prevalence of maternal hypotension caused by spinal anesthesia varied across the research, making it practically unable to set standards and develop a regional care plan.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: The study is Observational prospective study.

Study Setting: This study was carried out among patients scheduled for Caesarean section. This study was conducted after obtaining permission from the institute's Ethical committee, scientific committee as well as approval of the West Bengal University of Health Sciences.

Place of Study: This was conducted at obstetric operation theatre of Nil Ratan Sircar Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata, West Bengal.

Period Of Study: One and half year (March 2020 – August 2021).

Inclusion Criteria: Patients in the age group of 18 – 30 years with singleton pregnancy, weight 45 – 70 kg, ASA I or II scheduled for Caesarean section was included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with

1. Obesity (BMI>35 kg/ m²)
2. Acute fetal distress
3. Chronic hypertension
4. Placenta previa.
5. Diabetes mellitus
6. Coagulopathy
7. Multiple pregnancies.
8. Renal and cardiac disease
9. Refusal for spinal anaesthesia

Sample Size: 56

- Group A: 28 Normotensive parturients.
- Group B: 28 Parturients with severe pre-eclampsia having BP> 160/ 110 mm of Hg requiring antihypertensive therapy.

Study Tools:

- Written informed consent form.
- Proforma for data collection.
- Multichannel monitor.
- 18 G intravenous cannula for fluid therapy.
- IV Ringer lactate, normal saline.
- 2, 5, 10 cc syringe.
- 26 G Quincke's spinal needle for subarachnoid injection.
- Cotton swab for testing touch sensation.
- 25 G hypodermic needle for pain sensation.
- Anaesthesia machine and drugs necessary equipment for airway and hemodynamic management.
- Umbilical vein blood gas analysis machine.
- Drugs like
 - Inj lignocaine 2% for local infiltration of injection site.
 - Providence iodine 5% for antiseptic dressing.
 - Inj pantoprazole 40 mg.

- Inj metoclopramide 10 mg
- Inj ondansetron 4 mg
- Inj atropine 0.6 mg ampule
- 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine
- Inj fentanyl 100 mcg
- Inj oxytocin 5 IU ampules
- Inj phenylephrine 10 mg
- Resuscitative drugs and instruments
- Monitoring scale:

- 1= hypoalgesia
- 2= analgesia
- 3= analgesia plus hypoesthesia
- 4= anaesthesia

Apgar score

Study Parameters:

- Heart rate
- Systolic blood pressure
- Diastolic blood pressure
- Mean arterial pressure.
- Any adverse events like hypotension, bradycardia.
- Total amount of phenylephrine required.
- APGAR SCORE 1 and 5 minutes after delivery of baby.
- Umbilical vein blood gas analysis of baby.

Modified Bromage scale

0= no motor impairment (able to move joints of knee and ankle)

1= unable to raise extended legs (able to move joints of knee and ankle)

2 = unable to raise extended leg and flex knee(able to move joints of ankle)

3= unable to move knee and foot

The level of sensory block was assessed using the pinprick test.

Result and Analysis

Table 1: Comparison of parameters between the Groups

	Groups	Mean	SD	P Value
Age (years)	A	23.54	3.40	0.438
	B	29.61	2.25	
Weight (kg)	A	64.18	7.37	0.330
	B	65.96	6.15	
Consumption of phenylephrine (mcg)	A	100.00	14.76	0.006
	B	28.57	6.18	
Apgar score of baby at 1 minute	A	8.75	0.75	0.858
	B	8.79	0.74	
Apgar score of baby at 5 minutes	A	9.32	0.61	0.521
	B	9.21	0.63	
pH of baby	A	7.35	0.07	0.536
	B	7.36	0.06	
PO ₂ of baby	A	38.89	1.39	0.125
	B	39.42	1.16	
PCO ₂	A	38.32	2.34	0.535
	B	38.71	2.37	

Table 2: Comparison of percent change of mean SBP in different time intervals from baseline between the groups

Time intervals	Groups	Mean	SD	p value
Baseline to 3 min	A	6.41	2.06	0.614
	B	8.77	3.51	
Baseline to 6 min	A	8.96	2.97	0.493
	B	14.33	4.15	
Baseline to 9 min	A	12.85	6.4	0.083
	B	14.34	1.55	
Baseline to 12 min	A	9.90	1.85	0.633
	B	14.79	3.99	
Baseline to 15 min	A	8.14	2.95	0.881
	B	16.24	2.02	
Baseline to 18 min	A	8.75	3.73	0.237
	B	21.05	4.25	
Baseline to 21 min	A	10.65	6.98	0.171

	B	18.97	6.79	
Baseline to 27 min	A	10.75	2.28	0.661
	B	15.82	3.52	
Baseline to 30 min	A	9.87	2.33	0.283
	B	16.71	2.51	
Baseline to 35 min	A	6.71	1.21	0.408
	B	16.65	2.19	
Baseline to 40 min	A	3.53	0.03	0.767
	B	10.90	3.72	

Table 3: Comparison of percent change of mean DBP in different time intervals from baseline between the groups

Time intervals	Groups	Mean Percent Change	SD	p value
Baseline to 3 min	A	16.00	3.48	0.394
	B	12.04	2.37	
Baseline to 6 min	A	18.24	7.56	0.537
	B	14.43	5.03	
Baseline to 9 min	A	17.91	2.66	0.106
	B	18.53	6.61	
Baseline to 12 min	A	17.04	4.31	0.072
	B	14.46	6.74	
Baseline to 15 min	A	23.52	7.32	0.221
	B	12.88	2.61	
Baseline to 18 min	A	20.04	6.58	0.194
	B	29.53	6.44	
Baseline to 21 min	A	13.77	3.75	0.520
	B	22.95	3.47	
Baseline to 27 min	A	23.54	4.47	0.087
	B	15.96	2.62	
Baseline to 30 min	A	24.09	7.38	0.331
	B	17.81	3.61	
Baseline to 35 min	A	18.15	3.27	0.192
	B	19.11	5.04	
Baseline to 40 min	A	14.57	4.64	0.882
	B	20.60	5.46	

Table 4: Comparison of hypotension between the groups

Groups	Yes		No		p value
	n	%	n	%	
A	21	75.0	7	25.0	0.031
B	16	57.1	12	42.9	

In Group A, the mean Age (years) (mean± SD) of patients was 23.54± 3.40. In Group B, the mean Age (years) (mean± SD) of patients was 29.61± 2.25. Comparison of mean Age (years) between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.438). In Group A, the mean weight (mean± SD) of patients was 64.18± 7.37 (kg). In Group B, the mean weight (mean± SD) of patients was 65.96± 6.15 (kg). Comparison of mean weight between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.330). In Group A, the mean phenylephrine consumption (mean± SD) of patients was 100.00± 14.76(mcg). In Group B, the mean phenylephrine consumption (mean± SD) of patients was 28.57± 28.57 (mcg). Comparison of mean phenylephrine consumption between groups was statistically significant (p=0.006). In Group A,

the mean Apgar score at 1 minute (mean± SD) of babies was 100.00± 14.76. In Group B, the mean Apgar score at 1 minute (mean± SD) of babies was 28.57± 28.57. Distribution of mean Apgar score of baby at 1 minute between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.858). In Group A, the mean Apgar score at 5 minutes (mean± SD) of babies was 9.32± 0.61. In Group B, the mean Apgar score at 5 minutes (mean± SD) of babies was 9.21± 0.63. Comparison of mean Apgar score of baby at 5 minute between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.521). In Group A, the mean pH (mean± SD) of babies was 7.35± 0.07. In Group B, the mean pH (mean± SD) of babies was 7.36± 0.06. Comparison of mean pH of babies between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.536). In Group

A, the mean PO₂ (mean± SD) of babies was 38.89± 0.07. In Group B, the mean PO₂ (mean± SD) of babies was 39.42± 1.16. Comparison of mean PO₂ of babies between groups was not statistically significant (p=0.125).

There is no statistical difference exists between the groups in case of comparison of percentage change of mean SBP, mean DBP in different time intervals from baseline. (Table 2 and 3)

Discussion

This prospective, observational study compared groups of patients who were scheduled for a Caesarean section. The institute's scientific committee, ethics committee, and West Bengal University of Health Sciences all gave their approval before this study could begin. From March 2020 to August 2021, this was done at the obstetric operation theatre of the Nil Ratan Sircar Medical College and Hospital in Kolkata, West Bengal. Patients between the ages of 18 and 30 who had singleton pregnancies weighing 45–70 kg, ASA I or II, and scheduled for Caesarean delivery were included in the research.

Group A consisted of normotensive parturients, while group B included patients with severe pre-eclamptic (BP > 160/110 mm of Hg) requiring anti-hypertensive therapy.

The sample size was determined using an 80% study power and a 95% confidence interval. The chosen sample size of 56 parturients was determined based on our pilot study, which altered the mean difference of MAP by 4 units (mean difference - 4 units, SD 5 units).

Saha D et al [6](2013) found that Thirty healthy (group 1) and thirty severe pre-eclamptic (BP > 160/110 mmHg) parturients (group 2) who satisfied the inclusion criteria, were over eighteen years of age, and were having an elective cesarean section were included in the research. The minimum SBP, DBP, and MAP reported by the normotensive group were lower, and there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Regarding SBP, DBP, and MAP, there was no statistically significant difference between the groups in our investigation.

Manimekalai N et al [7] (2014) observed that there was an increase in HR (p<0.001) and a very significant drop in both SBP and DBP following the giving spinal anaesthesia. But over the same time frame, there was no discernible change in the CO, CI, or SVI (p>0.05). This change peaked one minute after spinal anesthesia for blood pressure and two minutes for heart rate, respectively. Conversely, there were no significant changes in SBP, DBP, or HR (p>0.05) but there were noticeable increases in CO (22.5%), CI (16.3%), and SVI (13.6%) after the

fetus was delivered. None of these data altered after the placenta was delivered; however, during the spinal implantation, the increased cardiac output and stroke volume index were sustained relative to the baseline. During our study, SBP, DBP, and MAP did not change significantly.

Mitra JK et al [8] (2013) found that hypotension, whose incidence in the study sample varied from 15.8% to 91.4%. It is recommended that the lowest absolute values at which vasopressor treatment should be commenced are a mean arterial blood pressure < 65 mmHg or a systolic blood pressure < 90 mmHg. Targeting a mean arterial pressure > 70 mmHg and systolic blood pressure > 100 mmHg is advised. These suggestions are based on an analysis of the obstetrics, critical care, and other relevant perioperative medicine literature. Practitioners should preferably maintain systolic blood pressure over 90% of the pre-spinal anesthesia baseline.

It is suggested to establish an ideal target in relation to baseline blood pressure and an absolute threshold for vasopressor intervention. To determine the impact of these guidelines on significant maternal and fetal outcomes, more research is needed.

We discovered that there was no statistically significant difference in the percentage of SBP, DBP and MAP falls from baseline up to 40 minutes. The highest percentage of SBP drop from baseline occurred at 18 minutes. In group B the maximum percentage of DBP drop from baseline occurred at 18 minutes. There was no statistical significant difference in the percentage of fall in SpO₂ or HR between the groups in our study. Group A parturients required more phenylephrine on average than group B parturients did.

Saha D et al [6] (2013) found that thirty healthy (group 1) and thirty severe pre-eclamptic (BP > 160/110 mmHg) parturients (group 2), over the age of eighteen, who satisfied the inclusion criteria for an elective cesarean delivery were included in the research. Phenylephrine was administered as a 50 µg bolus dose when MAP decrease below 30% of the baseline. The Apgar score was taken one minute after the baby was born. The normotensive group's mean phenylephrine demand (151.1 ± 70) was substantially larger (P < 0.0001) than that of the pre-eclamptic group (48.3 ± 35).

In our investigation, parturients in Group A consumed more phenylephrine [mean± standard deviation (mcg)] [100.00±14.76 (mcg)] than those in Group B [28.57±28.57 (mcg)], a statistically significant difference (p=0.006).

Kinsella SM et al [9] (2018) found that Hypotension is typically the effect of the sympathetic vasomotor block caused by spinal anesthesia for a cesarean delivery. Maternal symptoms like as nausea, vomiting, and dyspnea are frequently seen in

conjunction with severe hypotension. Low Apgar scores and umbilical acidosis are two detrimental outcomes on the fetus that have been related to the degree and duration of hypotension.

According to our research, Group A patients had higher rates of hypotension [21 (75.0%)] than Group B patients [16 (57.1%)]. which ($p=0.031$) was statistically significant.

Helill SE et al [10](2019) observed in the field of obstetrics, hypotension following a cesarean section done under spinal anesthesia is still frequently encountered. Ephedrine crosses the placenta more than phenylephrine and may change fetal physiology, although it has not been shown to affect fetal Apgar or neurobehavioral scores.

Nikooseresht M et al [11] (2016) found that The one-minute Apgar score was substantially lower in preeclamptic parturients (8.4 ± 0.7 versus 7.2 ± 1.5) ($P = 0.001$), but there was no significant difference between the two groups five-minute Apgar ratings. As it is associated with a lower risk of hypotension than previously believed, their findings support the safety of utilizing low-dose bupivacaine spinal anesthesia in severely preeclamptic women undergoing cesarean births. At one and five minutes after birth, the newborns in our research had comparable Apgar ratings in each group.

Belachew BG et al [12](2023) found that maternal hemodynamics are complicated by spinal anesthesia, which also puts the parturient at risk for serious cardiovascular issues. A total of 140 parturients—70 in each group—who had cesarean deliveries while under spinal anesthesia participated in a prospective cohort study. With the exception of MAP after 15 minutes, which was comparable between the two groups with $p = 0.638$, the mean % change in SBP, DBP, and MAP following spinal anesthesia showed a statistically significant difference between the normotensive and preeclamptic groups. We discovered that Groups A had a higher baseline to 3 minutes percentage change of mean DBP [16.00 ± 3.48] than Groups B [12.04 ± 2.37], although this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.394$).

In our study, Baseline to 6 min percentage change of mean DBP was higher in Groups A [18.24 ± 7.56] compared to Groups B [14.43 ± 5.03] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.537$).

We found that, Baseline to 9 min percentage change of mean DBP was more in Groups B [18.53 ± 6.61] compared to Groups A [17.91 ± 2.66] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.106$). In our study, Baseline to 12 min percentage change of mean DBP was higher in Groups A [17.04 ± 4.31] compared to Groups B [14.46 ± 6.74] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.072$).

Belachew BG et al [12] (2023) found that maternal hemodynamics are complicated by spinal anesthesia, which also puts the parturient at risk for serious cardiovascular issues. With the exception of MAP after 15 minutes, which was comparable between the two groups with $p = 0.638$, the mean % change in SBP, DBP, and MAP following spinal anesthesia showed a statistically significant difference between the normotensive and preeclamptic groups. We discovered that Groups A had a higher baseline to 15 minutes percentage change of mean DBP [23.52 ± 7.32] than Groups B [12.88 ± 2.61], although this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.221$).

In our study, Baseline to 18 min percentage change of mean DBP was higher in Groups B [29.53 ± 6.44] compared to Groups A [20.04 ± 6.58] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.194$).

We found that, Baseline to 21 min percentage change of mean DBP was more in Groups B [22.95 ± 3.47] compared to Groups A [13.77 ± 3.75] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.520$).

In our study, Baseline to 27 min percentage change of mean DBP was higher in Groups A [23.54 ± 4.47] compared to Groups B [15.96 ± 2.62] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.087$).

Tamiru SM et al [13] (2022) showed that Maternal hypotension is a common problem during spinal anesthesia that can be harmful to the fetus as well as the mother. Up until 30 minutes, vital signs (MAP, HR, SBP, DBP, and MAP) were obtained every 3 minutes; after that, they were collected every 5 minutes. The volume of intraoperative fluids required as well as the newborn Apgar scores was noted at one and five minutes postpartum. The data's distribution was confirmed using the Shapiro-Walk test. Preeclamptic patients (31%) had hypotension less frequently than healthy parturients (59.5%) (within 30 minutes after spinal anesthesia). Prior to or after the administration of spinal anesthetic, there was no statistically significant difference in the heart rates of the two groups.

We found that, Baseline to 30 min percentage change of mean DBP was more in Groups A [24.09 ± 7.38] compared to Groups B [17.81 ± 3.61] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.331$).

In our study, Baseline to 35 min percentage change of mean DBP was higher in Groups B [19.11 ± 5.04] compared to Groups A [18.15 ± 3.27] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.192$).

We found that, Baseline to 40 min percentage change of mean DBP was more in Groups B [20.60 ± 5.46] compared to Groups A [14.57 ± 4.64] but this was not statistically significant ($p=0.882$).

Conclusion

In a prospective comparative study, we examined the differences in hemodynamic parameters between severe pre-eclamptic parturients and normotensive parturients. In our study, normotensive parturients had a larger proportion of decline of MAP than parturients with severe pre-eclampsia, however the difference was not statistically significant. Furthermore, we found that parturients with severe pre-eclampsia needed less phenylephrine than normotensive parturients. Between-group differences in the APGAR scores of newborn at 1 and 5 minutes after birth were not statistically significant. In our investigation, we did not find any statistically significant variations in mean pH, PO₂, or PCO₂ of the newborns between two groups.

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